

FIBRE BUNDLE PULL-OUT TEST FOR THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The fibre bundle pull-out test constitutes a testing method that can be used to establish informative characteristic values for the adhesion of different fibre/matrix combinations both rapidly and without any major outlay on apparatus. In this paper the production of the specimens with thermoplastic matrices as well as the testing procedure are described. Different exemplary results show the suitability of the fibre bundle pull-out test to determine characteristic adhesion values for a fibre/matrix combination of glass and PP.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of fibre reinforced plastics are influenced to a decisive extent by the quality of the bond between the reinforcing fibre and the plastic matrix. Fibre/matrix adhesion can frequently be improved by treating the surface of the fibres or by adding coupling agents to the matrix. Different methods have been developed for measuring the characteristic values of fibre/matrix adhesion in order to permit statements to be made on the way in which different fibre modifications, and also variations in the process conditions employed to produce the fibre composite, influence the fibre/matrix adhesion. Apart from indirect measuring methods, such as the short-time bending test for determining interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), direct measuring methods have also become established, such as the single fibre fragmentation technique (SFT), the push-in test and the single fibre pull-out test [1].

DETERMINING FIBRE/MATRIX ADHESION BY THE PULL-OUT TEST

Of the direct measuring methods, the pull-out test constitutes a particularly simple, defined test configuration in which a pure shear stress state prevails in the fibre/matrix interface (under idealised conditions). When an individual filament is pulled out of a droplet of matrix in the single fibre pull-out test, it is possible for the maximum shear stress prevailing in the boundary layer τ_B to be determined as a characteristic value of the fibre/matrix adhesion using the following equation:

$$\tau_B = \frac{F_{\max}}{A} = \frac{F_{\max} \cdot d}{\pi l_e} \quad (1)$$

where

- F_{\max} = force required to debond the filament from the matrix,
 A = area of boundary layer,
 l_e = length of filament encapsulated,
 d = filament diameter.

Although the single fibre pull-out test permits the encapsulated area A to be determined as accurately as possible and hence permits precise calculation of the adhesion characteristic value τ_B , one drawback encountered in the single fibre pull-out test is the very small size of the specimen. The fine filaments are difficult to handle, with the result that the specimens can be damaged as they are being produced already. Since the pull-out tests have to be carried out under the microscope, and the forces at play are in the centinewton range, it is not possible for conventional universal testing machines to be used.

The high outlay involved in the preparation and test engineering for single fibre pull-out tests prompted the IKV to consider the development of a test method which would supply informative fibre/matrix adhesion values for fibre composites both rapidly and simply. In the fibre bundle pull-out test, therefore, it is not individual fibres but bundles of fibres that are introduced into the plastic matrix. This considerably facilitates the production of the specimens and the execution of the tests. In addition, the reinforcing fibres are tested in the form in which they are found in the actual component.

The fibre bundle pull-out test was first developed for thermoset matrix materials [2]. In the light of the increasing significance of fibre composites with a thermoplastic matrix, the technique for producing the specimens was modified in such a way that the reinforcing fibre roving could be fully encapsulated in the thermoplastic matrix.

PRODUCTION OF THE FIBRE BUNDLE PULL-OUT SPECIMEN WITH A THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX

The biggest problem encountered in the encapsulation of reinforcing fibres in a thermoplastic matrix is the relatively high viscosity of the thermoplastic melt. In order to achieve the best possible degree of wetting of the fibre bundles, the mould set out in Fig. 1 was constructed for the production of specimens. The top section of Fig. 1 shows the mould in the open position, viewed from above, while the middle section of Fig. 1 contains a longitudinal section. The external dimensions of the mould are 330 mm * 40 mm * 55 mm. On the right-hand side of the mould (in Fig 1) is an area in which a 2 mm thick strip of matrix material can be placed. Next to this area, on the left, comes a 2 mm wide flow channel. Nine lengths of roving are placed in the mould at right angles to this flow channel in order to produce the specimens. The lengths of roving are embedded between two strips of teflon or graphite film in order to prevent them from being damaged by the bright metal surface of the mould and to seal the flow channel.

To produce the specimens, the ready-prepared mould (with the fibre bundle and matrix strip in place) is placed in a combined heating/cooling unit and first of all heated. Once the strip of matrix has melted, the melt is pressed into the flow channel with the aid of a slide bar. The melt then flows round the fibre bundles. The pronounced flow of melt means that the individual filaments are completely wetted. If required, holding pressure can be exerted on the melt via a further slider bar which is mounted on the open, opposite side of the mould.

Figure 1. Mould for production of fibre bundle pull-out specimens

Once the flow channel is completely full the mould is cooled and dismantled, and the solidified strip of matrix with the fibre bundles embedded in it can be removed. The strip of matrix is divided up into nine individual specimens, with one of the two free ends of the roving being cut off in each case. Following this, the corresponding surfaces of the matrix plaques are ground until they are smooth.

TEST METHOD

The specimen is clamped into the tensile testing machine with a specimen clamp developed specially for the fibre bundle pull-out test. The set-up is depicted in Fig. 2 and essentially comprises two edges, one of which is notched. The fibre bundle is guided through the notch so that the matrix plaque is supported on the two edges.

The end of the roving that is still free and which had sandpaper glued to it before is clamped into conventional clamping jaws. The upper clamping unit is on a cardan mount and is also capable of axial displacement in order to smooth out any alignment errors between the upper and lower clamp. This effectively prevents the build-up of transverse forces in the roving. The parameters of force and displacement are recorded during the fibre bundle pull-out test.

Figure 2. Specimen clamp for fibre bundle pull-out test

EVALUATION OF THE TEST

The force/displacement curve in the fibre bundle pull-out test is essentially the same as that seen with single fibre pull-out tests. It is presented by way of example in Fig. 3 for a fibre/matrix combination of glass and PP.

Figure 3. Force/displacement curve in a fibre bundle pull-out test

In the first phase between "0" and "1", the fibre roving and the matrix initially undergo elastic deformation which is proportional to the increasing load. On account of the pronounced viscoelastic material properties of the PP there is a clear flattening of the curve profile in the region of higher forces and hence increasing shear stresses in the fibre/matrix boundary layer.

At $F = F_{max}$ ("1"), the fibre debonds from the matrix. A crack develops in the boundary layer between the fibre roving and the matrix surrounding it. The shear strength in the boundary layer, which has to be overcome for the fibre to debond from the matrix, can be used as a measure of the fibre/matrix interfacial adhesion.

Between "1" and "2", the pure elastic deformation of the matrix and the fibre bundle relaxes. The third phase, delimited by points "2" and "3" shows the force curve as the now "loose" fibre bundle is pulled out of the matrix plaque. With a constant advance rate, the ever-smaller length

of fibre in the matrix causes the depicted linear reduction in friction force on account of the increasingly small contact surface that exists between the fibre and the matrix.

The fibre bundle pull-out tests are evaluated with the aid of Eqn (1). There is, however, an essential difference between single fibre and fibre bundle pull-out tests when it comes to the determination of the encapsulation surface A of the fibre roving. Whereas in single filament pull-out tests the boundary layer area can be readily determined from geometrical relationships providing that the filament diameter is known, in the fibre bundle pull-out test this area has to be determined optically after the test has been carried out.

Since the fibre bundles are completely wetted, which causes the individual filaments to stick together, the crack in the fibre bundle pull-out test generally occurs along the outside contour of the embedded fibre bundle. The remaining circumference is scanned with a digitiser and thus measured directly. The precise depth to which the fibre bundle was embedded is measured by means of micrometer calipers on the matrix plaque once again. The measured circumference is smaller than the true circumference of the fibre bundle, since the make-up of the fibre bundle from individual filaments and the associated increase in surface is not taken into account in the visual determination of the circumference. On the basis of theoretical considerations, the true roving surface ought to be some $\pi/2$ times the measured surface. All the shear stress values referred to below have been calculated on the basis of the measured circumferential surface.

DETERMINATION OF CHARACTERISTIC ADHESION VALUES FOR A FIBRE/MATRIX COMBINATION OF GLASS/PP

INFLUENCE OF FINENESS OF ROVING

As can be seen in Fig. 4, the shear stress withstood by the fibre/matrix boundary layer decreases as the diameter of the roving rises and the size of the encapsulated area increases. This is because the greater the surface that is cast in, the greater the likelihood will be of defects occurring in the boundary layer between the fibre and the matrix. These defects, such as particles of dust on the fibre surface, can have the same effect as notches and thus reduce the quality of the interfacial bond between the fibre and the matrix.

Figure 4. Dependence of shear strength τ_B on encapsulation area

INFLUENCE OF TESTING TEMPERATURE

Figure 5 shows the curve of the characteristic fibre/matrix adhesion value τ_B as a function of the testing temperature. It is seen that the highest shear strength values are measured at a temperature of -40°C ($\tau_B = 22 \text{ MPa}$). The temperature of -40°C is considerably below the glass transition temperature, T_G , of PP, which is at approximately -20°C . A pronounced fall in the fibre/matrix adhesion is seen in the region of T_G and at 140°C , the mean shear strength of the fibre/matrix boundary layer is only 1.4 MPa .

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of shear strength τ_B (glass/PP) and shear modulus G of PP

Apart from the profile for τ_B , Fig. 5 also contains the shear modulus G of the matrix material as a function of the temperature. The parallel course of the two curves would seem to indicate that the quality of fibre/matrix adhesion is a direct function of the mobility of the chain segments of the matrix material in the boundary layer. The fact that the shear strength curve is shifted towards slightly higher temperatures than the shear modulus curve is attributable to the different matrix morphology, with different thermal properties, which prevails in the boundary layer close to the glass fibres, by comparison to the inside of the matrix. Microscopic investigations do indeed reveal transcrystalline areas in the matrix in the vicinity of the fibre surface.

INFLUENCE OF SURFACE TREATMENT

On account of the pronounced differences in polarity between the polypropylene matrix and the glass fibre roving, the glass fibres are treated with a coupling agent sizing at the manufacturer's already. In order to establish the efficiency of two different coupling agents, fibre bundle pull-out tests were conducted with comparable glass fibre rovings that had been given two different coupling agent sizings, A and B, by the manufacturer. As is clear from Fig. 6, the specimens treated with coupling agent A displayed the highest shear strength values for the fibre/matrix boundary layer. Fig. 6 similarly shows the result of an XPS analysis of the two glass fibre sizings. Sizing B contains a clearly higher proportion of polar groups than sizing A. The nonpolar nature of the PP matrix means that the affinity, and hence also the adhesion, of the type A roving to the matrix is greater than that of type B.

Fig 6. Shear strength τ_B and XPS analysis for different coupling agent sizings

PROSPECTS

The fibre bundle pull-out test constitutes a testing method that can be used to establish informative characteristic values for the adhesion of different fibre/matrix combinations both rapidly and without any major outlay on apparatus. Apart from the matrix material of PP with glass fibre rovings, the IKV has also successfully conducted the fibre bundle pull-out test with the thermoplastics of LCP and PEEK and both carbon and natural fibres.

Since the influence of fibre/matrix adhesion on the mechanical properties of fibre mat reinforced thermoplastics (e.g. GMT) has not been quantified so far, reduction factors established with the aid of fibre bundle pull-out tests are to be implemented in analytical formulations for determining the strength of materials of this type.

It would be possible to further develop the testing technique so as to permit material that has already been plasticised in a laboratory extruder to be conveyed directly into the flow channel. This would make it possible for thermoplastics to which relatively unstable coupling agents have been added, to be processed into pull-out specimens without having to be reheated.

REFERENCES

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